

Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Europium-, Terbium-, Dysprosium- and Thulium(III) with some Oxyacids, Thioacids and Phenols

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The present paper describes a potentiometric study on the complex formation constants and inter correlation of oxyacids (glycollic, lactic and malic acid), thioacids (thioglycollic, thiolactic and thiomalic acid) and phenols (catechol, protocatechuic acid and pyrogallol) complexes with Eu^{III}, Tb^{III}, Dy^{III} and Tm^{III} in aqueous solutions at a fixed ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 M$ and at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants were determined (Table 1) according to the method of the Irving and Rossotti¹. The order of the formation constants of the binary complexes are found to follow the order : glycollic acid < lactic acid > malic acid, thioglycollic acid < thiolactic acid > thiomalic acid, catechol < protocatechuic acid < pyrogallol. The stability constants of glycollate, thioglycollate and catecholate complexes are found to be in the order : Eu < Tb \leq Dy \geq Tm. This is agreement with the ionic radii and ionic potentials of the trivalent lanthanide ions.

The proton-ligand formation of phenols were found to be higher compared to thioacids². The more electronegative phenolate oxygen atom and trivalent lanthanide ions experience stronger electrostatic interaction which contrib-

utes to the stability of these complexes. The resonance effect of electrons in phenol possibly plays some role for which the M-O bonds are very strong in phenolate-lanthanide complexes.

Malic acid acts as a tridentate ligand but its complexes have lower stability than the corresponding complexes with glycollic acid and lactic acid which act as bidentate ligands. This may be due to bigger size of the malic acid, which possibly exerts steric hindrance and lowers the stability of the malic acid complexes.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and metal nitrates solutions were standardised by acid-base³ and complexometric⁴ methods. The proton-ligand and binary metal-ligand formation constants were determined in aqueous media at $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄) at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹. A 1 : 10 metal-ligand ratio was used for the equilibrium study. The nitrogen gas was passed through the solution to provide an inert atmosphere. A Control Dynamic pH meter fitted with a combination glass electrode assembly was used. The values of proton-ligand constants (pK_1^H ,

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND BINARY METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF OXY, THIO AND PHENOL COMPLEXES*

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand				Eu ^{III}		Tb ^{III}		Dy ^{III}		Tm ^{III}	
	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	pK_3^H	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$						
Glycollic acid	10.74	3.47	—	6.36	5.48	6.77	6.22	6.74	5.89	6.69	6.05
Lactic acid	11.12	3.57	—	7.12	6.21	7.08	6.50	6.86	6.09	6.55	5.85
Malic acid	11.58	4.81	3.19	5.93	5.14	6.78	5.68	6.61	5.99	6.51	5.99
Thioglycollic acid	10.22	3.29	—	5.93	5.12	5.51	5.49	5.61	5.39	5.71	5.03
Thiolactic acid	10.30	3.41	—	6.18	5.46	6.09	5.34	5.62	6.42	6.44	5.94
Thiomalic acid	10.54	4.39	2.91	5.91	5.85	5.97	5.29	5.65	5.82	5.93	5.65
Catechol	11.30	9.34	—	9.56	—	9.78	—	9.88	—	9.98	—
Protocatechuic acid	10.77	8.94	—	10.16	—	10.36	—	10.45	—	10.58	—
Pyrogallol	12.25	8.97	4.43	10.48	—	10.58	—	10.68	—	11.08	—

*Standard deviation = ± 0.05 log units.

pK_2^H and pK_3^H) and metal-ligand constants were calculated from the potentiometric titration data.

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